

STATISTICAL GUIDELINES FOR AUTHORS

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The present Guidelines (or its future updated version) are available online at <https://animal-journal.eu/animal-journal/instructions-and-policies/>.

BEFORE YOU START

The position of the journal regarding statistics

i *animal* recognises that there is no unique way of statistically analysing data but considers that, for readers, editors and reviewers to understand the research and the statistics, precise and thorough reporting and clear presentation are required.

The present guidelines are focused on defining the reporting requirements for each section of an article while providing advice to authors on good practice in communicating and reporting research.

Ethical and transparent practice is essential to good practice and reproducibility in statistics. "It is easy to lie with statistics. It is hard to tell the truth without it." – Andreijs Dunkels

The quality of the reporting of statistical analyses and results is key to the soundness of a study's interpretation and conclusions. In reporting and discussing results, it is essential that the magnitude of a response is given, together with a statement of its uncertainty, and its relevance to the study's aims and objectives.

animal recognises that the current guidelines are not exhaustive and only address some of the basic and most frequent conditions in animal science. The focus is on designed experiments, but some advice is also provided for other types of study.

For more guidance, authors are advised to consult statisticians or experienced colleagues, or to contact the journal. A more detailed exposition of some of the statistical ideas presented here can be found in Bello and Renter (2018).

Ethics in statistics

Ethics in statistics is just as important as ethics in other aspects of research in animal science. In what follows the importance of framing a research hypothesis as a statistical hypothesis is stressed. This should be done *a priori*, i.e., the hypothesis should be the precursor to the study. In designed experiments methods running counter to this principle are questionable, and mostly involve the 'headlining' of unexpected results, searching for significance among potentially chance findings and overstating conclusions. In all other types of research (e.g., exploratory data mining) methods without a formal hypothesis or research proposal need to be properly justified.

The journal expects authors to avoid the following unethical practices in statistics:

- **HARKing:** Hypothesising After the Results are Known refers to the presentation of unexpected statistical results as if they had been formally tested;
- **Cherry-Picking:** refers to the selection of only statistically significant results to support a hypothesis whilst ignoring other non-significant results;
- **P-Hacking:** is the process of analysing data in different ways or in different combinations solely in order to obtain a statistically significant result;
- **Fishing expeditions:** this refers to the detailed examination of association between variables (and combinations of variables) in search of statistically significant effects which are often interpreted as cause-and-effect relationships despite the lack of *a priori* hypotheses and no consideration of false positive findings;
- **Spinning:** over-interpretation to make results seem more impressive than they are, i.e., unjustified claims of generalisability or causality.

Transparency and reproducibility in statistics

Considering the reproducibility crisis in science generally, the journal strongly encourages transparency to improve reproducibility of the research it publishes.

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- *animal* recommends that data, models and software developed in the course of the research are deposited in an official repository (<https://www.re3data.org/>). If this is the case, provide the full reference.
- *animal* recommends accurate and thorough reporting of the Material and methods and of Results of studies. The journal supports the use of reporting guidelines available at <https://www.equator-network.org/reporting-guidelines/>.
- *animal* also recommends that you deposit your code for the statistical model, as programmed in the relevant software, in an official repository or that you include it in the Supplementary materials.
- When a compartmental model has been developed, the full model equations (diagram, name, description and units of all parameters and variables) should be provided in the manuscript or in Supplementary Material. Also the model should be deposited in an official repository (<https://www.re3data.org/>) and accessible to reviewers.

How to use this guide?

This guide explains the reporting requirements presented in the Instructions for Authors. Advice for good practice is available for each reporting requirement.

For each (sub-) section of an article, you will find the reporting requirements, and explanations if you need any.

Step 1. Identify the reporting requirements for each (sub-) section of an article

Reporting requirements for section xxx	Details in
#1. The reporting requirements for a given (sub-) section of the article are listed here	This link will take you to the relevant section for further information
#2.	

Step 2. Read tips to quickly find guidance

Item

Find here the key information required to fulfil the reporting requirements.

Step 3. Read further explanations, if you need any

Good practice

Find here definitions and advice on good practice.

Avoid pitfalls

Insufficient reporting may result in your submission being returned to you or rejected at submission; it may also increase the duration of the peer-review process.

The journal invites authors to avoid frequent errors and, as relevant to their study, carefully consider the reporting of

- The design of the study, whether it is experimental or observational
- The 4Rs of the design, Randomisation, Replication, Reduction of Variation (Blocking) and Representativeness
- The experimental or observational unit, as relevant
- Diagnostics, e.g., normality, outliers
- Excluded or missing data
- The number of observations or the degrees of freedom
- Uncertainty measures, e.g., error terms
- Treatment comparison methods
- The search for association or causal relationships in correlation or regression analysis, and for patterns or classes in multivariate analyses

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- Software
- Shortcomings in the design
- The scope of inference of your results and conclusions

Also, the journal considers the followings as serious flaws

- The study design not matching the research hypothesis or question or is fundamentally flawed
- The statistical model not matching the study design
- Lack of replication
- Suspicion of the assumptions or quality of data not being met
- Suspicion of bias, or confounding factors not being included or discussed
- Multiple comparison for dose response
- Cherry-picking or incomplete reporting of results
- Over-interpretation (spinning)
- A compartmental model not deposited in an official repository and unavailable to reviewers.

INTRODUCTION

Reporting requirements	Details in
#1. State your research hypothesis and/or describe your research objective, depending on the section of the journal you are submitting to. The hypothesis or objective should follow directly from the rationale and critical analysis of available knowledge presented in the Introduction	§ Hypothesis or question
#2. The research hypothesis should match the study design (whether experimental or observational) and be linked to the data, the model and the statistical analysis, as appropriate.	§ Hypothesis or question

Hypothesis or question

Evaluation by editors and reviewers starts with a research hypothesis or a statement of the research objective.

Beforehand, check whether the section of the journal you intend to submit to considers hypothesis or data driven research (see Publication Policies at <https://animal-journal.eu/animal-journal/instructions-and-policies/>).

Good practice

It is important to set out clearly what you wish to demonstrate with your research findings, i.e., what the objectives are, or what the hypothesis is. This will determine the study design, the data measurements, the data structure or the relationships to explore between variables or factors (breeds, treatments, etc.) based on the response of single or multiple factors. Manuscripts should contain a clear and accurate statement of the research hypothesis or objective, which should be justified by the rationale and critical analysis of available knowledge presented in the Introduction.

Framing a research hypothesis as a statistical hypothesis is critical. It must be something that can be tested: the null hypothesis or 'no difference' hypothesis is usually tested by some sort of statistical test. Even though it is the alternative hypothesis (of difference) that is frequently proposed, it is the comparison against the null hypothesis that becomes important. This should be done *a priori*, i.e., the hypothesis is the precursor to the study.

This is the starting point for editors and reviewers to evaluate whether the hypothesis, the data, the proposed model and the statistical analysis match the research objectives.

Cox and Donnelly (2011) write:

“It is often helpful to think of investigations as occurring in the following steps:

1. *formulation of research questions, or sometimes hypotheses;*
2. *search for relevant data, often leading to*
3. *design and implementation of investigations to obtain appropriate data;*
4. *analysis of data; and*
5. *interpretation of the results, i.e., the translation of findings into a subject-matter context or into some appropriate decision.”*

In many journals, the Statistical Guidelines tend to focus on the third and fourth of these, i.e., the design and analysis of experimental data, with less emphasis on the other three. The present updated guidelines of *animal* stress the importance of all steps. In emphasising these five steps, we wish to encourage researchers to think about their research programme, and not just the analysis of results.

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MATERIAL AND METHODS – STUDY DESIGN

Use a separate and short sub-section ‘Study design’ at the beginning of your Material and methods to describe the nature and structure of your study, in particular whether your study is experimental or observational. This subsection should not include detailed descriptions of animals, housing, management, measurements and treatments, the later belong to separate sub-sections.

Reporting requirements	Details in
#1. Define the nature of your data (experimental, observational or from a collated database), and describe its structure as a two-dimensional array, e.g., how factors of variation, variables and experimental/observational units are set up in columns and rows of your data spreadsheet.	§ Data
#2. For designed studies, name the experimental design you have used (e.g., completely randomised or randomised block design).	§ Simple balanced designs
#3. For non-designed studies, specify the factors of interest, as you would in a designed study.	§ Data
#4. Define and justify the nature of the experimental units (e.g., individual animals, groups/pens) and of the observational units (if any) in your study.	§ Experimental Units
#5. Indicate the method of randomisation (e.g., between animals, pens and treatments).	§ The Four <i>R</i> 's
#6. Explain how the replication / sample size was chosen.	§ The Four <i>R</i> 's
#7. Describe the system of blocking if any.	§ The Four <i>R</i> 's
#8. Indicate the population of inference that your experimental unit is representative of.	§ The Four <i>R</i> 's
#9. Report the <i>a priori</i> power of your experiment if you can.	§ Power

Study design

An important distinction is made between experimental and observational studies. An experimental study is one in which all key elements, including the treatments or interventions, are under the control of the experimenter, and randomisation of treatments to experimental units takes place. By contrast, in an observational study, some factors, and in particular the allocation of animals / units to treatment groups, are outside the experimenter’s direct control. Welham et al. (2015) may be a useful reference to consult. Designed experiments usually comprise two components: the design structure (that is, the experimental units, any organisation between them such as blocking, and any subdivisions of the experimental units such as observational units, e.g., time samples or observations on sub-units); and the treatment structure, describing how treatments or interventions are imposed (randomised) onto the design structure (Casella, 2008, §1.5). Although there is inevitably some cross-over between design and treatment, what is important here is the experiment’s design structure, the treatment structures are discussed later.

In studies with observational data there is no randomisation. The data are collected from an observational study or collated from a database, in which there is an association of the output (or response) data with a ‘treatment’ / exposure or input data (covariate) not under the researcher’s control. The implications of this are that the scope of any inference is compromised by the generalisability of the research data.

The study design is described by the structure of the collected data (both treatment and response). Structure is important because it will determine how those data are analysed. For observational data, the relationship between treatment and response is most often a simple relationship, which may be exploratory, whereas in designed experiments the design imposes a more specific model on the data.

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Data

i *The nature (experimental, observational ...) and the structure of your data are critical in determining the statistical analysis and interpretation of your results. They should be relevant to your research objective. Your study design must match the structure of your data.*

Data are often presented in tabular (or matrix) form with experimental units as rows; identifiers, factors (treatments or other factors of variation / structures) and measured variables as columns.

Do not describe data quality here but in a different sub-section ('Validation and Quality Assurance', see Instructions for Authors at <https://animal-journal.eu/animal-journal/instructions-and-policies/>). Remember all data should be checked and verified before any statistical analysis. Potential confounding effects should also be identified.

Good practice

An important distinction is made between experimental and observational data (or from a collated database); the interpretation of the results (i.e., the inferences that can be drawn) will depend on the assumptions that can reasonably be made about their nature and generalisability. Experimental data refer to studies where the treatments or interventions are under the experimenter's control, and the allocation of experimental units (e.g., animals) to treatment groups occurs via randomisation. Results from series of experiments (in location or time) may still be considered experimental if conducted under controlled conditions, though such series lead to more complex error structures that need to be carefully interpreted (see later). Observational data relate to studies where the allocation of animals / units to treatment groups are outside the researcher's direct control. They may consist of database records, such as milking or stock records, genetic / breeding studies, epidemiological data, etc., or may be determined from animals / samples taken from different sources or studies. For both experimental and observational studies, the preliminary methods of data analysis may often be the same.

The structure of the data effectively determines what statistical methods to use. Most data sets will emerge as a two-way table (or data matrix) with experimental and/or observational units as rows, and all variables (factors, results, etc.) as columns. Such a formal structure enables the scientist to distinguish between factors that are based on treatments or structure (often an experimental design or database), the variables of interest, and the experimental or observational units. When many measurements are taken on an individual (columns in the data matrix) there may be marked correlations between them, so that they are not independent. Potential confounding effects should be identified. There may be more complex data sets, as, for example, in animal breeding, which may have a more intricate relational structure.

- For some models and meta-analyses, the data are essentially meta-data, i.e., not original data, but parameters or coefficients derived from original studies and analyses. These may not conform to the data structure model above.
- Many -omics studies are from designed experiments in which the impact of different treatments or interventions is being examined for a large set of variables.
- Any -omics analysis should first ensure that data fulfil the need for adequate statistical design for sample collection before data are even collected. This is often overlooked until after the data are collected!" (Gromski et al., 2015). The statistical design should be clearly presented.
- Data from -omics studies would have a similar format to many other studies: the data structure or data matrix would, for instance, contain samples or subjects as rows and metabolites as columns.
- When measurement (e.g., scoring) may be subject to subjective bias, the bias can be reduced by 'blinding' the operators so that they do not know what treatment has been applied. For both experimental and observation trials it is important to consider whether 'blinding' is necessary or even possible.

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Simple Balanced Designs

i Simple designs (completely randomised, randomised block, Latin Square, cross-over) apply to a balanced number of observations for each treatment. These designs lead to standard models for analysis.

Good practice

- Simple designs such as Completely Randomised Designs, Randomised Complete Block Designs with or without factorial treatment structures, and also Latin Square and Crossover Designs, are particularly useful because they are balanced, such that all levels of the factors for treatments and organisation (such as blocks) occur equally.
- In simple designed experiments the differences between treatments or interventions (e.g., Control vs. Treatment, or Treatment A vs. Treatment B) carry considerable inferential weight. We frequently assume that this difference is strongly replicable or transferable, though there will be limits. For instance, when a second treatment factor is introduced and interactions occur, i.e., the response to levels of the second factor are different at levels of the first factor. Classification factors such as animal sex, breed or (say) parity in dairy experiments cannot always be assumed to be additive, and results should be checked for interactions.

Experimental Units

i The experimental unit is the smallest unit to which an individual treatment is imposed. Experimental units should be independent of each other. By contrast the observational unit is the smallest unit on which a response will be measured. These definitions apply to all types of studies, whether experimental or observational.

In many studies a single measurement is taken on each experimental unit, in which case the experimental unit and the observational unit are the same. When there are multiple measurements on the same experimental unit (e.g., animals within groups, repeat samples on the same animal or samples over time) then there is no true replication, and these measurements are observational units. Indicate observational units where they occur.

How are the experimental and observational units chosen? Are they representative of the target population, and what are the eligibility criteria for their choice? Explain and justify any exclusions, dropouts, etc.

Good practice

- Distinguish between experimental and observational units where appropriate.
- The experimental unit is the smallest unit assigned to a treatment and the level at which randomisation applies in designed experiments. Experimental units should be independent of each other. The number of experimental units determines replication. By contrast, the observational (or measurement) unit refers to multiple measurements (such as measurements over time or space) made on an experimental unit.
- The definition of an experimental unit depends on whether treatments are applied to the individual animal or to a group of animals. When treatments are applied to groups of animals, the measurements at the animal level are not necessarily independent of each other, and the experimental unit is the group. To achieve replication (necessary for an estimate of SEMs), there need to be two or more groups for each treatment for a residual variance term to be estimated.
- Pseudo-replication occurs when the treatment or primary intervention applies to the whole group (the experimental unit) but measurement/sampling is done on each observational unit (e.g., measurement of individual animals). So, different animals within a group, i.e., within an experimental unit, are pseudo-replicates, not experimental replicates. In these conditions, measurements at the observational unit level may seem independent but they may be affected by inter-animal behaviour such as the feed intake of individual animals.
- Where individual animals are measured but, for experimental purposes, animals reside in groups, there is a fundamental difference between the inter-group variance (derived from the experimental structure and its replication) and the between animal variance within a group or replicate. These variances should remain distinct and should never be combined. The between

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animal variance is almost always smaller than the replication variance, and combination of these two measures ‘dilutes’ the experimental variance leading to false conclusions.

- Pseudo-replication limits the generalisability of the results, and should be recognised and highlighted by authors.
- When treatments are applied at the animal level but animals are housed in groups the independence of animals in the same pen cannot be assumed and should be justified in order to declare the animal as the experimental unit.
- When, however, a treatment is applied and measured at the level of an individual animal, and interactions between animals do not influence the application of the treatment, and measurements are independent of any interactions between animals, then the animal might be considered as the experimental unit. Authors should, nevertheless, justify their choice and address the scope of inference of the results.
- With trials in applied conditions when animals are managed in groups with a single group per treatment such as on large research or commercial herds, what is the experimental unit? Essentially, if each of two large herds is assigned (randomised) to one of two interventions, there are really only two experimental units and two treatments, i.e., no replication, so there is no measure of variability. Any observed difference between the outputs of the two herds is not really attributable to treatment differences because there will be various confounders: the herds, the farms or lots, the treatments, the housing conditions, etc. One way of considering the problem is to sub-sample the herds (by, say, measuring groups of animals from within the herd in pens), thereby providing some form of replication. This is still, however, pseudo-replication (see above), because the variance being measured is between groups of animals from the same experimental unit, and not from replicates of the intervention. Sometimes, a uniformity trial might be a very useful test of how variable different herds might be. Replication becomes even more complex when animals move in and out of pens during the progress of a trial, and it is difficult to really understand how animals might interact with one another and with their changing environment.
- Where there are multiple observational units (e.g., aliquots of single samples), but no true (sample) replication, then any analysis provides an intra-sample variance (essentially a measure of instrument variability). Multiple independent samples are necessary for estimating inter-sample variance.
- Data derived from measurements over time on the same animal (experimental unit) are effectively observational units which are distinguished by time as a factor. Such data will be correlated (and not independent) and the correlation structure may be quite complex. Any analysis needs to take this into account. See *Repeated measures data* in the [material and methods - Statistical ANALYSIS OF DATA of data](#) section. The argument above is made with reference to animals as experimental units, but the same principle applies to feed, blood and other biological samples. It is essential to distinguish between samples taken from different individuals and sub-samples taken from an initial sample – they do not have the same variances and the variances should not be combined.
- These ideas and their implications are addressed more fully in the papers by St Pierre (2007) and Bello & Renter (2018).

The Four R’s of Experimental Design

The cornerstone of experimental design is sometimes referred to as the four R’s: Randomisation, Replication, Reduction of Variation (more commonly referred to as Blocking) and Representativeness.

Randomisation is about how, for instance, animals are assigned to pens and pens to treatments. A lack of randomisation (in database experiments, or studies where samples are taken on the same experimental unit over time, or from several animals in the same experimental unit) and representativeness may limit the inferences (generalisability) of the results.

Replication ensures that treatment differences can be detected.

“Block what you can, randomise what you cannot”. Use blocking to eliminate unnecessary variation in your experimental sample, e.g., age, size, parity, breed, etc., and then randomise the treatment / intervention within the blocks.

Representativeness of experimental units to the population of interest is important to the conclusion of your study.

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Good practice

Important points to consider when planning an experiment are: the method of randomisation, the level of replication, the system of blocking (if any) to be used, and the representativeness of the experimental units to the population under study. These should all be described and justified.

- Randomisation is the process of assigning animals (or other experimental units) to treatment and control groups in a manner that offers each unit an equal chance of being assigned to any particular group (see, e.g., Casella, 2008). Randomisation generally ensures unbiased comparisons and estimates of residual (error) variance. It is also the mechanism that enables inference to be made between treatments or interventions, i.e., it justifies a cause and effect relationship. It refers to how the treatments (controlled experimental factors or interventions) are assigned to experimental units (by randomisation or other allocation) and to pens (if any).
- Animal pens, whether occupied singly or multiply, are a factor in an experimental design, and they should be assigned to treatments at random. Thus, for example, if there are eight pens (labelled 1 to 8) available for an experiment with two treatments (say, T and C), then a random permutation of the letters TTTTCCCC should be assigned to pens 1 to 8, and a different permutation used for every experiment. Never repeat the same randomisation in different experiments (unless it happens by chance!). If you're unhappy with that, re-randomise.
- Replication should be sufficient to ensure that treatment differences of practical importance can be detected. Determining the sensitivity (or power) of your experiment depends on the effect size you wish to determine (the important difference), the estimated residual variance of the experiment and the replication. This relationship is usually inverted by defining the confidence you want in the result (the power) and determining the replication. General purpose software is available for this online.
- Subsampling of experimental units does not provide true replication. “Most researchers are aware of the need for replication but often mismatch the scale of the replication relative to the treatments being applied” (Quinn and Keogh, 2023).
- Blocking allows major components of variability to be reduced from estimates of treatment effects and experimental error. This is done by stratifying the available experimental units into groups which are similar – essentially grading the differences between units – and making comparisons between groups (or blocks). Thus, for example, if animals are stratified by weight into groups of similar weight, and treatments applied to animals within blocks, the comparisons between treatments within blocks will be more precise. Note that the analysis for such experiments should include a blocking factor. Alternatively, the initial measurement can be included as a covariate. Note that the two methods rely on different models.
- Representativeness. It is also important to ensure that the experimental process is representative of that for which inference is to be made, i.e., does the experiment ‘look like’ the situation or the population it is trying to emulate? This is why the research context should be described. So, for example, a study looking at individually-housed animals may not be representative of group-housed animals, or those in applied conditions. The inference of the results is therefore limited to the conditions of study.

Power

The power of a test is useful at the planning stage in determining the required size of an experiment or sample. It is also useful to interpret the generalisability of the results.

If possible, report the power of your experiment, determined a priori, for the measurements that you consider as being the most important to test your research hypothesis / question.

Good practice

- Statistical power is the likelihood of a significance test detecting an effect when an effect of a certain magnitude exists.

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- Power is mainly influenced by replication, the effect size one wishes to achieve, and the significance level.
- The power of a test is important at the planning stage in determining the required size of an experiment or sample (replication) to ensure that a statistically significant result will be achieved.
- Power calculations have no role in the analysis of data but are useful in assessing the generalisability of the results: where an effect is judged not significant in an experiment, an examination of the power of the experiment may be helpful in understanding whether the judgment is appropriate or should be examined in further experiments.

Whenever possible, the power of the experiment should be determined a priori, for the measurements that are considered as being the most important to test the research hypothesis / question. Most medical research insists on a power calculation at the design / proposal stage. This is essentially a measure to eliminate proposals that are unrealistic, or are unlikely to satisfy ethical, medical or commercial requirements. In medical trials, the desired replication is usually achieved by recruiting subjects over time and conducting multi-centre trials. In agriculture, and animal science generally, the constraints are different and under-powered trials are often conducted because the resources are limited or time-constrained, and replication across time or season is a possibility. Nevertheless, a preliminary power calculation is valuable, and can be useful for assessors (funders, editors, reviewers and readers) to understand the context of a research programme. Power calculations are generally used to determine the level of replication necessary to give some certainty to the chances of detecting a favourable result when it exists, but the calculation depends on an estimate of the likely variability of the trial. In animal experimentation there may be a good prior estimate of likely variability, but care should be taken not to deliberately understate the variability.

MATERIAL AND METHODS – MODELLING

You may use a Modelling sub-section of the Material and methods to describe your meta-analytic or compartmental modelling approach.

Reporting requirements	Details in
#1. A thorough description of the model is imperative to ensure reproducibility. See details in the respective sections.	§ Meta-analysis or § Compartmental models
#2. When a compartmental model has been developed, report its reference in the official repository in which it was deposited and report its access to reviewers and editors.	§ Compartmental models

Meta-analysis

i *Meta-analysis is subject to a rigorous methodology and reporting. Model evaluation, limits and generalisability of the results should be specified.*

Meta-analysis is a method of statistical analysis that combines the results of several scientific studies investigating the same phenomenon or process. The data are essentially meta-data, i.e. not original data, but parameters, estimates or coefficients derived from original studies and analyses.

Good practice and reporting requirements

- Meta-analysis is subject to a rigorous methodology and reporting. Compliance with the Cochrane collaboration (<https://cochrane.org/>) using the Prisma reporting checklist (<http://www.prisma-statement.org/>) ensures a consistent standard of research methodology and a rigorous reporting.
- The criteria that need to be met in the contributing papers should be described. Unpublished studies should not be used unless they are thoroughly described in Supplementary materials or in a data paper with the detailed experimental conditions and the results.
- All papers used in the meta-analysis must be listed as part of the Supplementary materials.
- The meta-design should be thoroughly described. Homogeneity vs heterogeneity among the selected studies are particularly critical to the generalisability of the conclusions. Sources of heterogeneity should be analysed, and potential confounding factors identified. Refer to Sauvant et al. (2020) for details.
- Describe how the study effect was introduced in the statistical model.
- Graphical representation of data is encouraged to visualise heterogeneity of data and potential collinearity.
- A critical evaluation of the models obtained should be presented, with an assessment of bias and of certainty. Statistical indicators of accuracy and precision (e.g. root mean square error and its decomposition into overall bias, deviation of the slope from unity and random error; coefficient of determination) should be provided.
- The limits and generalisability of the results should be discussed.

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Compartmental models

i *Compartmental models should be thoroughly documented and evaluated. In the absence of external validation, limits and generalisability of the results should be specified.*

Reviewers should have access to the model for the peer-review.

Compartmental models include some degree of biological understanding in their structure. They may be deterministic or stochastic, static or dynamic. Compartmental models are constructed at a minimum of two levels of description consisting of a collection of compartments that are linked by ordinary or partial differential equations. These equations can be derived from the analysis of mechanisms that underlie the systems behaviour or following a data-driven approach (Thornley and France, 2000).

Good practice and reporting requirements

- Thorough description of the models is imperative to ensure reproducibility. The full model equations (diagram, name, description and units of all parameters and variables) should be provided in the manuscript or in Supplementary Material. For stochastic models, information on how the stochasticity is set in the model should be detailed.
- Information on simulation factors such as the initial conditions of state variables should be provided.
- Specifications about the software and methods used for model simulation and calibration should be provided. It is important to list the functions integrated in the simulation software, with a statement of the method used in such functions, e.g., ‘The model was solved using the “rk4” function (the fourth-order Runge-Kutta method) implemented in R’.
- Model evaluation of the structure and parameterisation is strongly recommended. It is particularly important in studies involving a model calibration routine but also applies to theoretical modelling work. Structural and parameterisation evaluation can be done via identifiability and sensitivity analyses, essential to avoid over-parameterisation.
- An identifiability analysis determines theoretically whether the model parameters can be uniquely identified for a given experimental setup (Munoz-Tamayo et al., 2018; Munoz-Tamayo and Tedeschi, 2023). The analysis can be performed *a priori* or *a posteriori* and information on the identifiability of the parameters should be reported. Non-identifiability does not necessarily mean that the model is wrong, but advises the reader to be cautious in the application of the model and its analysis.
- A sensitivity analysis assesses the influence of the parameters on the model output (Iooss and Lemaître, 2015).
- If model calibration and model validation are done, statistical indicators of accuracy and precision (e.g. root mean square error and its decomposition into overall bias, deviation of the slope from unity and random error, and/or coefficient of determination) should be provided.
- If no external validation has been conducted, the limits of the model should be clearly explained.
- The model should be deposited in an official repository (<https://www.re3data.org/>) accessible to reviewers.

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MATERIAL AND METHODS - STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF DATA

Use a separate sub-section ‘Statistical analysis of data’ at the end of your Material and methods to present the methods of statistical analysis of results. Sufficient details must be given of the statistical methods used to provide an understanding of the statistical analysis and results, and to allow replication.

Reporting requirements	Details in
#1. Report the methods used to check the distribution of data (e.g., normality) and identify outliers. Justify and describe any transformation of the data.	§ Diagnostics
#2. Describe the model for statistical analysis mathematically or in words, as well as the type of analysis used. In case of non-experimental study, justify the statistical model you have used.	§ Linear models and analysis of variance
#3. Explain and justify the use of more complex models, e.g., mixed models; describe the scope and limitations of any random effects.	§ Random Effects and Mixed Models
#4. Specify treatment structure and the methods used to compare treatment means.	§ Treatment structure & comparisons
#5. Specify the <i>P</i> values you considered for significance. If different from 0.05 justify them.	§ Statistical significance
#6. For correlation and regression, clearly state if a causal relationship is assumed or only an association between variables.	§ Correlation and Regression
#7. When exploring relationships within a matrix of data, state whether you are looking for patterns in the data or you want to classify new measurements.	§ Multivariate methods
#8. For multivariate analysis, report data validation methods and false discovery rate.	§ -omic studies
#9. Report the computer software you have used, the name of the software company, the package or procedure, the version and year of release, and the algorithm (i.e., the choice of arguments within the called function or procedure).	
#10. We recommend you include the code for the statistical model, as programmed in the relevant software, in the Supplementary materials.	

Simple descriptive statistics

i Descriptive statistics are recommended to make the readers understand the nature of your data.

Good practice

- Many results exhibit a symmetrical distribution and are usually described by the means (or other estimates as relevant), some indication of the dispersion of the data (usually SE or SD), and the number of experimental units or the number of degrees of freedom of the residual variance depending on the analysis. These latter two statistics (SE and degrees of freedom) enable the reader to judge the precision of the central (mean or other) estimate. Note the distinction between SD and SE: SD is a measure of the variability in a sample or population, SE is a measure of the prediction of the estimate (SEM is also used to refer to the standard error of the mean). Note that the SD of a variable is the square root of the variance.
- An alternative to the use of SEs, as a measure of uncertainty, is to give the estimate together with a Confidence Interval usually expressed at the 95% level. The Confidence Interval expresses the range within which the estimate is expected to lie 95% of the time. It is determined

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by adding or subtracting the SE times the appropriate upper and lower points of the t -distribution, which is dependent on the number of degrees of freedom for the residual variance. Confidence Intervals and estimates plus SEs are effectively interchangeable, though Tables are easier to read with SE(M)s. Where the degrees of freedom is of the order of 20 or more, a simple approximation of the 95% Confidence Interval is given by $\text{mean} \pm 2 \times \text{SEM}$.

- For categorical variables the natural descriptive statistics are the proportions (or percentages) for individual categories (possibly restricted to the most important categories with remaining categories pooled together as ‘other’, if necessary). For ordinal categorical data (e.g., scores), the minimum and maximum values as well as the median, rounded off to its nearest category, can alternatively be presented.
- For other analyses (e.g., heterogeneous, and unbalanced data) and when data are approximately symmetrically distributed, means (or other estimates as appropriate) must be given with their corresponding SDs (or SEs, but please make clear!) and numbers of experimental units. Note that where sets of data with different replication are being compared, SEs are not the same for different means: $\text{SE} = \text{SD} / \sqrt{n}$, where n is the replication or number of values.
- For non-normal data, report median, minimum, maximum and lower and upper quartiles. If a transformation is effective in ‘normalising’ the data, use the mean and SE of the transformed data. Visualisation of the distribution is encouraged. Box-Whisker plots are a very good way of visualising non-normal data.

Non-parametric methods

i *Non-parametric or distribution-free methods relate to tests and models where no assumptions are made about the distribution of the sample. They are most frequently used where data lack pattern or are distributed over a wide range.*

Good practice

- It is always important to look at data using a summary plot such as a histogram or a Box-Whisker plot to see if its distribution is symmetrical, skewed or more complex.
- In some instances, the data do not appear to conform to a particular (parametric) model such as the normal distribution, e.g., the data do not appear symmetrical, or the range is heavily skewed, in which case a non-parametric or distribution-free method may be appropriate.
- It is often useful to describe such data in terms of medians (central values) and inter-quartile ranges (the difference between 25th and 75th percentiles) rather than means and SDs. The range itself, or a histogram of the data may also be useful descriptors
- Statistics based on the ranks of observations are one example of such statistics and these play a central role in many non-parametric approaches. The most common procedure for testing the difference between two samples or treatments is the Mann-Whitney-Wilcoxon test (see, e.g., Quinn and Keough, 2023).

Diagnostics / Outliers

i *Quality of data is critical to any analysis. Check assumptions. All data should be subjected to appropriate scrutiny: the use of standard diagnostics, such as checks for normality (or symmetry) of residuals, visual checks for linearity, outliers, etc. have been undertaken. Observations which seem to be inconsistent with the main body of data should not be excluded from the analysis without good reason.*

Good practice

Standard diagnostics, such as visual checks for normality (or symmetry) of residuals (e.g., histograms and Q-Q plots), Box & Whisker plots of data, identification of outliers and plots of observed *versus* fitted data should be done prior to any analysis. These are generally routine with modern software, and do not

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need to be presented, though an acknowledgment of their use is encouraged. Box & Whisker plots can be helpful in some presentations.

Data should be examined for gross errors, e.g., recording or transcription errors, which should always be reported, and not excluded without justification. Exclusion of observations seemingly inconsistent with the main body of data should be reported and justified. Do not routinely omit observations or results that fall outside arbitrary limits such as $\bar{x} \pm 3 \times SE$. If in doubt, it may be useful to analyse the data both with and without an anomalous value to assess the sensitivity of the analysis to its presence.

Linear models and analysis of variance

Linear model is a term that covers designed experiments, data-base and other observational data models (usually analysis of variance or **ANOVA**) and also includes mixed models and multiple regression (incorporating analysis of covariance, sometimes called **ANCOVA**). A linear model is one in which the response variable is a simple linear (additive) combination of the explanatory variables weighted by regression coefficients (0s or 1s in the case of ANOVA). Analysis of covariance incorporates a regression component into a standard ANOVA model; the covariate is usually a measure taken before treatment that is expected to reduce the residual variance in an experiment. So, in an experiment to ascertain weight gain of animals, the initial weight of the animal may be an appropriate covariate. This is the classical definition of a covariate, though the word is more generally used for any ancillary measurement in a linear model.

Statement of the model

i The statement of the model confirms both the experimental design and the form / nature of the analysis. It enables the reader to understand the methods used to analyse the data. The model used for analysis must match the structure of the experiment.

In designed and observational experiments, where there is a factorial structure (i.e., where each level of one factor appears with each level of another), then the interaction terms should be included in the model by default. Their exclusion needs to be justified.

Good practice

- The simplest ‘statistical’ statement of a Completely Randomised Design is expressed as follows:

$$\text{mathematically, } Y_{ij} = \mu + \alpha_i + \varepsilon_{ij} \quad \text{where } i = 1, \dots, t \quad \text{and } j = 1, \dots, r$$

or in words: response = overall mean + treatment effect + error (or residual)

Where Y_{ij} represents the response variable, μ represents the mean, α_i the ‘fixed’ effect of treatment i , and ε_{ij} the residual effect associated with replicate j of treatment i . Note that the treatment effect is the difference between the treatment mean and the overall mean. This is the simplest type of ‘designed’ experiment, though this model is common for other types of data where different treatments are being compared. Other designs (e.g., randomised complete blocks, factorial models, etc.) incorporate further fixed effect parameters.

- Simple regression models are represented by an equation of the form:

$$Y_i = \alpha + \beta X_i + \varepsilon_i \quad \text{where } i = 1, \dots, n$$

with similar interpretation to the above: Y_i represents the response variable, while X_i is the independent or predictor variable; the parameter β is often referred to as the slope. Multiple regression models simply extend the number of independent variables. The analysis of covariance is a hybrid model incorporating both a standard design model with a further regression term for the covariate.

- Random effects models look like fixed effects models mathematically – the difference is that the parameters represent unobserved random terms with zero means but variances (different from the residual variance) that need to be estimated.

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- Mixed models are combinations of fixed and random effect models. The mathematical formulation looks similar to linear models but incorporates extra terms representing different strata of variation corresponding to the random effects such as farms, regions, years, etc.
- In designed and observational experiments, where there is a factorial structure (i.e., where each level of one factor appears with each level of another), then the interaction terms should be included in the model by default. The relegation of some forms of interaction to the error/residual term should be stated and justified, and be apparent from the mathematical statement. If using a ‘word’ model make sure it contains all the appropriate factors.
- In some more complex studies, particularly in observational studies and regression analyses where several variables are examined simultaneously, the higher-order interactions between factors may be excluded from the statistical model based on statistical tests when exploring potential relationships. Such decisions need to be explained.

Analysis of variance

i When there are more than two treatments in a designed experiment, an ANOVA is appropriate for most types of data.

Good practice

- With balanced designs with ‘fixed’ factors, the total variance is partitioned into variances due to factors (structural and treatment) and a residual variance. The residual variance gives rise to the estimates of standard errors (SEs / SEMs) of the treatment means and allows for testing differences among treatments using an *F*-test.

$$SEM = \sqrt{\text{residual variance/number of observations per treatment}}$$
- The null hypothesis in ANOVA is that all the treatments are equal, so a statistically significant effect (usually $P < 0.05$) states that the treatments are deemed different but does not specify how (see [Multiple comparison tests](#)).
- In balanced designs (when there is the same number of observations for each treatment or treatment combination) the treatment means are simple averages of the data, and the SEs of individual treatments are all the same as they have equal replication, assuming the residuals are homogeneous, i.e., consistent. In unbalanced designs SEs will be different for different treatments because of differential replication, but the use of SEs of differences (SEDs) between pairs of treatments can be a helpful substitute. Alternatively, specify the number of observations per treatment considered to calculate the reported SEM.
- For most measured variables, the assumption that residuals are normally and independently distributed is appropriate. Most standard methods (in particular, ANOVA) are robust to deviations from this assumption. Note that it is the residuals obtained after fitting regression or ANOVA which should be normally distributed, not the raw data.
- When the different sources of variation are not all fixed, see the section on [Random Effects and Mixed Models](#) below.
- ANOVA or linear mixed model? ANOVA is far more efficient than a linear mixed model when using balanced data, but the latter method is necessary if the data are correlated (usually true for time to response data) or when there is unequal variation between groups (VSNI Team, 2022).

Analysis of covariance

i Analysis of covariance aims to reduce variation of treatments when the covariate is known to influence the response and is continuous. It is more an analysis than a design issue, but it can be seen as pertinent to design strategy.

Good practice

- Two important assumptions are made: the covariate is related to the response, but NOT related to the treatment.

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- Covariates are used to reduce variation, but, differently from blocks. They use a form of regression that supplements the underlying ANOVA model.

Transformation / Generalised Linear models

i Data transformation or other techniques are helpful when the residuals obtained after fitting regression or ANOVA are not normally distributed or when variance varies with effect size. Count and proportional data usually need different techniques.

Good practice

- If the residuals are skewed or otherwise non-normally distributed; if the residual variance is not constant because a transformed scale was used; or if effects (treatment differences) are not constant on the original scale of measurement, e.g., the variance increases with the response means, special methods may be required, such as a transformation of the data or a generalised linear model (GLM).
- Most frequent statistical analysis methods apply to continuous data (data measured on some continuous scale such as weight). For other types of data, whether discrete (general count data or ‘discretised’ numbers of days), nominal (e.g., breed of animal, allele, etc.), or binary (two-state, such as presence / absence, etc.), a simple transformation – see next bullet point – may be used. When counts are large, they may be treated as if continuous.
- Some commonly used transformations are the square root, for data in the form of counts (Poisson data), and the logistic transformation, for binomial data. If the variance seems to vary as the square of the mean as it may do in growth data, a logarithmic transformation may be useful. If SEs are not constant for comparisons on the original scale, estimates, SEs, and test results are best given on the transformed scale. The equivalent effects on the original scale are most easily given in the form of Confidence Intervals.
- If the results of an analysis under transformation are similar to those for the untransformed data it is more transparent and simpler to present the untransformed results.
- An alternative is to fit a GLM (Dobson and Barnett, 2018). This allows the problems of variance heterogeneity and additivity of effects to be tackled separately. A linear model equates the expected value of an observation to a linear combination of factors (as above), whereas in a GLM a transformation of the expected value is equated to the linear combination. The transformation is called the link function, and different link functions (transformations) are used for different underlying models. A linear model is therefore also a GLM where the link function is simply the identity.
- Traditionally, the analysis of count data, usually binomial and multinomial data (contingency table analysis) was done with the X^2 statistic using a chi-squared test. The two approaches (X^2 and GLM) usually produce similar results, though GLMs are generally preferred for binomial and count data nowadays. Survival data, and data with heteroscedastic variance is also usually analysed using GLMs.
- Note that where the data are ordinal (e.g., ordered categorical or score data), then conventional methods such as averaging or the use of linear models may not be appropriate, due to the discrete nature of the data and the fact that scores are not necessarily equally-spaced. Alternative methods involve treating the data as nominal, or unstructured and using a multinomial model, which makes no assumptions about order but may be useful for comparing treatments or groups. More complex models assume an underlying logistic model, which effectively relates the ‘cut’ points between scores as being defined by a logistic regression. Three methods are set out in Ch. 8 of Dobson and Barnett, 2018) to which the reader is addressed. See also Grace-Martin (2020).

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Random Effects and Mixed Models

i *Random effects are used when different sources of variation enter the data. Inclusion of random effects should be justified and interpretation of random effects should recognise the limits to the generalisability of the results.*

Mixed models contain both fixed and random effects.

Good practice

Effects are considered random when they cannot be related to fixed interventions – the assumption is made that they are a random sample of a larger population. For instance, factors such as animals, farms or years are not generally of interest in themselves, but the variability between animals, and between farms or years needs to be taken into account in the model. Classification factors such as breed, gender and parity are important in many animal experiments, and it is useful to consider these as fixed effects, although such factors may well induce interactions with other treatment or intervention factors, so it is important to replicate. In complex experiments which incorporate replication over years or across farms or regions, modern software offers solutions in the form of mixed models where factors replicated over time and space are considered random, while interventions / treatments are fixed.

- Mixed models are those which incorporate fixed and random effects together. The assumption is made that random effects are a ‘random sample’ of a larger population.
- If random effects are representative of the sorts of conditions one may expect to encounter, they can be included in a linear mixed model that includes random effects to account for this extra structural variability, as well as fixed effects such as treatments which directly affect the response.
- Random effect models contain more than one source of variation. They can cater for correlated data. With random effects, the interest is in the variability of the samples and not in the impact of each sample within the factor. Such models are common in attempting to understand variability or in the determination of a sampling strategy – trying to determine where to focus sampling effort.
- Scope and limitations of random effects (years, farms, regions, breeds etc) should be described. The generalisability of the data, i.e., the extent of the inferences that may be made, may be limited by confounding and bias. For instance, depending on the origin of random effects data, there may be a geographical bias (the limitation of the data to a particular region), a selection bias (in the sense that only the ‘best’ farms may contribute to the database, e.g., if it relies on data from applied trials), or there may be a trend over years – an impact of climate change, say.
- Care is needed in their interpretation because different sources of variation need to be separated, and the (usually) unbalanced nature of the random source of data can cause confounding and bias. The discussions in Mead et al. (2012, §9.3), and Cox & Reid (2000, §6.5) are cautionary.

Treatment structure & comparisons between treatments

A treatment design is “the manner in which the levels of treatments are arranged in an experiment” (Casella, 2008). In simple designs there is often just a single set of levels of a treatment factor where the levels are usually considered ‘fixed’ because the impact of a treatment is considered as having a specific (fixed) effect which one is trying to estimate. Factorial designs involve more than one treatment factor, where the levels of each treatment are crossed with each other to form a full factorial set. The overlaying of treatment design on experimental design is more difficult as treatment structure becomes more complex.

Treatment design is crucial for selecting the appropriate method to test treatment differences. In most instances, comparisons between treatments will be conducted within the context of linear models for normally distributed data. These will lead to *t*-tests (for two treatments) or *F*-tests (for more than two) and may be pursued further using multiple comparison procedures, though this is contingent on the *F*-test being statistically significant (see, e.g., Casella, 2008). In the case of GLM (for non-normal data) *F*-

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tests or chi-squared tests may be used (see Dobson and Barnett, 2018). See, also, the reference to ordinal data above.

Factors with quantitative levels (dose-response studies)

i Where a treatment factor has well-defined quantitative levels, a quantitative level model such as a linear or polynomial response function model should be fitted to the effects of that factor.

Good practice

- Where a treatment factor has well-defined quantitative levels, a quantitative level model such as a linear or polynomial response function model should be fitted to the effects of that factor.
- The fitted model describes the overall response to the treatments and the individual treatment responses will not normally be presented or discussed. Such models partition the variance usefully into ‘lack of fit’ (demonstrating the fit of the regression model) and ‘pure error’ (the residual variance from the ANOVA).
- The ANOVA model will generally require a dose-response or simple regression analysis within the standard between-treatment model, i.e., the treatment sums of squares should be broken down into polynomial (e.g., linear and quadratic) contrasts.
- Where there are different treatments each with their own dose levels (a nested model), separate dose-response equations can be used for each treatment within the ANOVA system.
- Dose-response models are not usually appropriate when the dose levels are ordinal as the levels are not necessarily equi-spaced, and there is usually no clearly defined interval between them.

Repeated measures data

i Repeated measures strictly refer to longitudinal data, where the same experimental unit is measured on multiple (n) occasions where $n > 2$. The repeated measures data are not independent. Their analysis requires appropriate methods of analysis to account for the degree of correlation between measurements.

Repeated measures do not apply when measurements are made on different animals at different times, because the measurements are independent and ‘classical’ methods apply, though care is needed when removing individual animals from a group over time as this may change the group dynamic.

Good practice

- When measurements are taken on the same experimental unit on multiple occasions, successive data are not independent they are correlated with one another. Their analysis often requires special methods that take into account the correlation structure between measurements.
- For some responses, such as animal weight or intake recorded over time, a summary measure such as the mean or the slope (of a regression of weight vs. time) for each experimental unit may be sufficient. Summarising the data to a single measurement eliminates the serial correlation.
- For repeated measures care needs to be taken in determining the nature of the correlation structure. The most common types are:
 - independent (i.e., all correlations are zero)
 - compound symmetry (all correlations are the same)
 - autoregressive (where correlations fall away with distance or time)
 - Toeplitz (a bit like autoregressive, but the link with time is less structured), and
 - unstructured (i.e., estimated from the data).

Procedures for such analyses are available in most common statistical packages such as SAS, R and SPSS, though many packages default to options 1 and 2, which are rarely justifiable. There are online tutorials (e.g., <https://stats.oarc.ucla.edu>) showing how to analyse various data sets

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using different structures in different packages. It is a common practice to look at different structures and choose the one with the lowest ‘goodness of fit’ statistic such as **AIC** (Akaike’s Information Criterion) or log-likelihood. However, if you use your data to estimate the correlation structure, and then analyse the data using those estimates the analysis is not independent of the input estimates! There is much to be said for choosing a structure based on *a priori* expectations.

- Correlation structures (between successive observations) can be complex and may not necessarily be consistent across treatments or time. It is always recommended that you ask whether the treatments have changed from one time point to the next. Where observations are taken at regular intervals there will tend to be a falling away of the correlation across time but that doesn’t necessarily imply a simple auto-regressive structure (see above).
- When considering sampling strategies for repeated measures it is sometimes surprising to realise that adjacent observations may be very highly correlated ($r > 0.95$, say), and that more sparse sampling of the timeline may help in better understanding the temporal effect as well as saving on sampling effort.

Multiple comparison tests

i Treatment means can be compared using multiple-comparison tests if and only if the ANOVA detects statistically significant treatment effects. The most robust comparisons are those planned pre-experimentally.

Do not use multiple comparison methods for dose response studies to differentiate dose levels – it is not consistent with the idea of a dose-response curve!

Good practice

- A well-designed experiment sets out to test a small number of clearly stated hypotheses, often with carefully structured treatments. In this case comparisons are determined a priori and there should be no need for multiple comparison tests, though a Bonferroni correction may be used.
- When comparing n treatments, there will be $n - 1$ degrees of freedom for ‘independent’ comparisons.
- When the treatment structure provides a logical basis for testing as described in various sections above (e.g., a dose-response study), the uncritical and indiscriminate use of multiple comparison procedures, such as Duncan’s method and the Student-Newman-Keuls test is not appropriate, primarily because the false error rate increases with the number of speculative tests performed. The use of multiple comparison methods for dose response studies to differentiate dose levels is not consistent with the idea of a dose-response curve. Methods that deal with pairwise comparisons are more powerful (see §2.9.1 of Casella (2008), for a brief explanation).
- There are other forms of contrast (comparison) that can be made between treatments – this is usually done pre-experimentally, i.e., the contrasts form part of the underlying hypothesis.
- Factorial structures in which all levels of one factor occur with all levels of the other, e.g., Factor A has a levels, and Factor B has b levels) lead to an experiment with ab treatment combinations. Such arrangements lead to more complex contrast structures, which, set up in the right way provide orthogonal contrasts.

Statistical significance

i Statistical significance should not be confused with practical or biological significance. The journal considers that the P value for significance is set at $P < 0.05$. If a different value is chosen, it must be thoroughly justified. The actual P value should be reported.

A ‘non-significant’ result does not demonstrate that there is no effect – it simply asserts that no effect has been detected “absence of evidence is not evidence of absence”.

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Good practice

- The 5% point ($P < 0.05$) of the test distribution has become something of a discriminator, but it was never intended to be that – the original use of $P < 0.05$ was more of a comment that the data were worth examining rather than that the result was truly meaningful. The fact that a result is statistically significant simply means that the result deserves some examination to ascertain its biological or practical importance.
- Give the actual P value rather than using the ‘coarser’ star convention (* $\sim P < 0.05$, ** $\sim P < 0.01$. etc.) except if $P < 0.001$.
- Equivalence testing examines whether new treatments (e.g., antibiotic replacements) are equivalent or non-inferior to ones in current use (Walker and Novacki, 2011). This involves defining a relevant difference a priori, which the new treatment must exceed. The burden of proof rests on this initial hypothesis. For noninferiority studies, the research hypothesis is that the new treatment is either equivalent or superior to the current treatment.
- Outcomes of statistical testing are commonly misinterpreted. Consult an authoritative source on the correct / incorrect interpretations of such testing, such as Greenland et al. (2016). Statistical hypothesis testing relates to hypotheses developed prior to data exploration, i.e., hypotheses reflecting primary study objectives. Reporting estimates with their associated uncertainty is more informative than quoting a P -value.
- A small real effect, of no practical importance, may be statistically significant in a very large sample, or an ‘over-designed’ experiment. Note that absence of a significant difference does not demonstrate equivalence unless the power of the study is sufficient. A non-significant difference in a trial does not mean that there is no effect, rather that no effect has been shown: your experiment may have been underpowered for the result you were hoping to achieve, or the data were more variable than your expectation.

Correlation and Regression

i Correlation can only ever imply that there is a linear relationship between two variables. Regression assumes that there is a causal relationship between two variables and regression analysis is used to predict one variable with the other.

Good practice

Correlation looks at the association between variables and is not a measure of a causal effect. By contrast, regression assumes that there is a direct causal relationship between the variables.

- Over-interpretation of correlations or associations should be avoided. A statistically significant correlation does not demonstrate any direct biological relationship.
- Regression models often use less structured data than designed experiments, and model the variable of interest Y against independent variables X_i ($i = 1, \dots, k$) where the data multiples (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k, Y) may come from different sources. Such models are often created to predict Y rather than simply describe it. Stepwise selection procedures may be used to reduce an unwieldy set of independent variables to a more manageable subset. There may be a large number of subsets, all giving approximately the same quality of fit. If the purpose of the regression is prediction, it may not matter which subset is chosen, whereas if the purpose is scientific understanding, it is more important that the reduced equation be biologically sensible than that it be chosen by a statistically optimal procedure.
- Regression can also be considered within the ANOVA structure of designed experiments with two or more quantitative levels. Goodness of fit is usually tested against the residual (replication) error term.
- Care needs to be taken when individual variables are highly correlated, usually known as multicollinearity; in this case, statistically significant effects simply reflect each other rather than reinforcing each other.

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Multivariate methods

Multivariate analysis provides a set of statistical techniques that examine the relationships within a matrix of data comprising experimental units and multiple variables: the methods generally explore the structures within the units. Methods should be chosen depending on the objective.

Classical Multivariate analysis

i Be clear with your objective. Unsupervised learning is essentially looking for patterns in the data, whereas supervised learning uses test data of known provenance to classify new measurements.

They do not demonstrate any causal relationships between variables, but they may result in hypotheses of causal relationships that will require independent testing.

Good practice

The Wikipedia entry for Multivariate Analysis (a very useful initial reference) offers 19 different types of multivariate analysis. The classification of these methods according to the newer nomenclature of unsupervised and supervised learning is useful:

- When the objective is to group the data (the units) in absence of *a priori* knowledge or expectations, then methods like principal component analysis (**PCA**) or some form of cluster analysis may be appropriate. This is unsupervised learning – one wishes to learn what the data has to tell us.
- When the objective is to demonstrate differences between groups when some knowledge is already available, then canonical variate analysis and multivariate analysis of variance (**MANOVA**) may be useful, and this is supervised learning. The known grouping within the data may have been derived initially from a discriminant function or set of functions that classifies a test set of candidates. Such methods are often used in areas such as epidemiology.
- Descriptions of these techniques, e.g., Hastie et al. (2009) may be helpful to some authors, particularly with regard to huge quantities of data such as in ‘-omic’ studies.

-omic studies

i False discovery rate should be estimated.

Multivariate methods applied to -omics data do not demonstrate any causal relationships between variables, but they may result in hypotheses of causal relationships that will require independent testing.

Good practice

Multivariate methods are well suited to large -omics data sets where the number of variables (e.g., genes, proteins, metabolites) is much larger than the number of samples (e.g., animals, cells). They have the appealing properties of reducing the dimension of the data by using instrumental variables (components), which are defined as combinations of all variables. Those components are then used to produce useful graphical outputs that enable better understanding of the relationships and correlation structures between the different data sets that are integrated.

- Many -omics studies are from designed experiments in which the impact of different treatments or interventions is being examined for a large set of variables. Any -omics analysis should first ensure that data fulfil the need for adequate statistical design for sample collection before data are even collected. This is often overlooked according to Gromski et al., 2015. The statistical design should be clearly presented. Data should first be subjected to validation, (to ensure accuracy, correctness of the data) and normalisation for commensuration (to ensure that metabolites with large values do not dominate) and then to an unsupervised method such as PCA to reduce the dimensionality of the data and eliminate correlated variables.

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- In -omics studies the number of variables of interest is usually much greater than the number of samples, and standard methods need to be supplemented by other techniques, such as basic univariate analysis, to interpret the results appropriately. The method of false discovery rate is commonly used and the false discovery rate should be estimated. A useful reference is Aggarwal and Yadav (2016).
- Care should be taken to make a critical use of algorithms produced by major software groups and of their ‘default settings’ for algorithms which may not be suited to many data sets. This is particularly true for standard techniques such as **PLS-DA** (Partial Least-Squares-Discriminant Analysis); other multivariate techniques should also be explored (Gromski et al., 2015).
- As data become more extensive and complex, it becomes difficult to validate or diagnose problems with the output. *Ad hoc* software produced by specialist -omics groups may offer more exploratory options.

More advanced statistical and chemometrics techniques are proposed and explained by Hastie et al. (2009) and the bibliography in Gromski et al. (2015) is extensive. Where possible, take advice from a statistician, a chemometrician or an experienced scientist. A useful mathematical discussion is given in Bickel (2022).

RESULTS – REPORTING YOUR RESULTS

The report of your statistical results should be informative enough to allow the reader to make independent judgments wherever possible but omit extraneous detail.

Reporting requirements	Details in
#1. Report and justify deletion of data or outliers	
#2. Carefully consider the most appropriate illustration of your results.	§ Tables or figures?
#3. Report the descriptive statistics (e.g., in Supplementary materials). They will help the reader understand what your data are.	
#4. Give estimates of the relevant statistics (mean values, regression coefficients, etc.) together with the appropriate SEs or Confidence Intervals of those estimates.	
#5. Report degrees of freedom (or number of experimental units), error terms (SEMs for ANOVAs) and exact P -values except if $P < 0.001$.	§ Statistics in tables
#6. In tables include the interaction effect if statistically significant.	§ Statistics in tables
#7. Pay attention to the number of meaningful digits determined by the precision of the measurement. The SE/SDs should be quoted to an extra digit relative to the mean.	§ Number of digits
#8. Be clear on which results are critical to your research hypothesis or question, and ensure you include relevant estimates, measures of uncertainty (SE or Confidence Interval).	

Tables or figures?

i Carefully consider whether including Tables or Figures. Do not report redundant or irrelevant information. Make Tables as concise as possible.

Good practice

- Tables are recommended when absolute values may be of interest to readers. Figures are recommended to express trends (not necessarily linear), such as response with time or dose etc.
- Tables and graphical representations should be as concise as possible and used for important points only. Secondary information can be relegated to Supplementary Tables.
- Summary statistics should be presented and several different forms can be used, such as a statement within the text, as a table, or in some form of Figure. Bar charts may be used, though they are wasteful of space when there are only a few groups. In situations where one wishes to draw attention to the distributions of different responses, Box-Whisker plots can be helpful, as they give some representation of range and distribution shape.
- Sometimes a simple tabular array can be more informative than a series of overlaid plotted lines.
- Bar charts usually present categorical, discrete or continuous variables grouped in class intervals – they are not really appropriate for means of continuous data: line plots are better, particularly for plotting means over time or distance, as they imply movement and difference.
- Authors are invited to be imaginative in the construction of Figures and not simply rely on default settings of some standard statistical and spreadsheet packages such as Excel in order to best illustrate the ‘story’ of their article.
- Graphical presentation of results in Supplementary Materials can complement tables in the main text. If a treatment factor is quantitative, simple line plots of different measures can be plotted against the quantitative factors (with appropriate scaling). Similarly, tables of compositional data (e.g., grouped metabolites, dietary fractions, etc.) can be presented as stacked bar plots, where the comparative size of each metabolite can be judged over different treatments.
- About the format of Tables and Figures, consult the Instructions for Authors.

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Statistics in tables

i Due consideration should be given to degrees of freedom (or number of experimental units), error terms and exact *P*-values.

When data are analysed by ANOVA, report the residual error term (SEM) in tables and not SE/SD for each treatment. Confidence Intervals are an alternative to SEMs but they can make tables more complicated except for simple comparisons.

When interactions are significant, report the individual means of each treatment.

Good practice

- In tables, treatments, means, degrees of freedom (or number of experimental units), SEMs and probability values are in columns, variables are in line. In the presentation of ‘busy’ tables, Confidence Intervals are an alternative to SEMs, but they tend to add to the complexity as each mean requires two additional numbers, a lower and an upper bound, whereas a single SEM is often sufficient for several means.
- The degrees of freedom on which the means and SEs are based or the number of experimental units per treatment should be given to help the reader compare estimates. In balanced experiments where the replication is the same for each treatment / intervention, there will generally be only one value which can be reported in the heading or provided in a footnote.
- When data are analysed by ANOVA and an assumption of homogeneous variance for all treatments is made, a residual error term, is given for each criteria/item/variable/trait in a separate column.
 - In balanced designed experiments where treatments are equally replicated, means and the pooled residual SE of the mean ($SEM = \sqrt{\text{residual variance}/\text{number of observations per treatment}}$) should be provided. Only one SE (SEM) need be given as it will be the same for all treatments. SEs should not be presented separately for each mean unless the means are based on different numbers of observations, or the heterogeneity of the error variance is to be emphasised.
 - In unbalanced designed experiments, for example where litter sizes do not turn out equally between groups of dams, where a herd does not contain balanced numbers of different breeds, or attrition (dropouts) cause differential replication between treatments SEMs will vary between treatments. There are several ways of dealing with this: if the difference in replication is quite small, an ‘average SE’ may be acceptable; alternatively, the SD can be quoted and the number of replications appropriate to each treatment should be indicated, recalling that $SEM = SD/\sqrt{r}$, where *r* is the replication. SEs should not be presented separately for each mean unless the means are based on markedly different numbers of observations, or the heterogeneity of the error variance is to be emphasised, i.e., the variability of treatment means is noticeably different.
- When interactions effects are statistically significant, all individual means and *P*-values should be presented in the tables because reporting the main effects has little meaning. If the interaction effect is not statistically significant, only the main effects of the factors need be presented.
- For generalised linear and/or mixed models that do not always provide results in an ANOVA-type layout, it is recommended that estimates of variance as well as the parameter estimates for fixed effects are presented.
- Give the actual *P*-value (to 3 decimal places) rather than using the ‘coarser’ star convention (* ~ *P* < 0.05, ** ~ *P* < 0.01, etc.) except if *P* < 0.001. If *P* > 0.05, give its value – do not write “NS”.
- Indicate differences between treatments (or comparison of mean values) using superscript letters, e.g., ^{a,b}.

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Number of digits

i Present only meaningful digits for means and SEs.

Good practice

Meaningful digits depend on the precision of the measurement.

- For mean values, 2 or 3 meaningful digits (not decimal places) are usually sufficient. Mean values should include all certain figures and the first ‘uncertain’ one. For a set of data, a ‘certain’ figure is one that varies little in its range (i.e., up to, say, three digits), whereas an ‘uncertain’ one can take any value. You may consider changing unit (e.g., from g to mg) to minimise the number of presented digits.
- The SD / SE should be quoted to one more place than the mean (e.g., for a mean value of 15, SE should be reported as 1.2) so that the reader can make their own comparisons.
- Providing too many digits can obscure the effectiveness of the presentation of the data.

DISCUSSION - DISCUSSING YOUR RESULTS

Reporting requirements	Details in
#1. Any shortcomings in design or analysis should be discussed with an indication of the possible effect on the results.	
#2. Be clear on what your critical results are. Include a discussion of the biological relevance of the determined magnitude of effects for those results.	§ Critical results
#3. Explicitly state the scope of inference, or generalisability and limits, of your results and conclusions.	§ Inference

Critical results

i When discussing your results, be clear which variables are the most important to test your research hypothesis or question.

Good practice

- In many studies, there will be specific variables that are imperative to the study, e.g., weight gain, milk yield, etc., but there will also be other ancillary variables which are related to the main variables and may be highly correlated with them. As a result, multiple statistically significant effects are not independent often replicating the same response. Do not make the assumption that such multiple effects strengthen or reinforce your inference: they may simply reflect the same overall effect. Similarly, be wary of multiple analyses of cumulative data, i.e., univariate analyses of the same response at different times.

Inference

i How general are the conclusions you are drawing from your results? To what extent do they depend on the set-up of your study?

Good practice

- The scope of inference of your results should be clear. Any shortcoming in your study design or statistical analysis should be discussed to inform readers of any limitation in the application of your results.
- A designed experiment is the 'gold standard' for the scope of inference, in that the only difference between two or more randomly selected samples is due to the treatments applied.
- In the absence of replication, speculative conclusions can be offered but not proven.
- Correlation or association between data is not a measure of causality. A statistically significant correlation does not imply causation. However, a hypothesis of causal effects can be taken forward for subsequent testing. Over-interpretation of correlations or associations should be avoided.
- A well-defined scope of inference will help writing the Implications section

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